

ELIXIR Commissioned Service DATAREX WP2

D2.2 End report on body of knowledge

Tier: Technology

Priority Area: T1, N4, P1

Thematic Area (if applicable): [Research Data Management](#)

Executive Summary

This D2.2 End Report on the Body of Knowledge documents the completion of Task T2.2 within ELIXIR's DATAREX WP2, focused on expanding and updating best-practice content for research data management (RDM), with particular emphasis on the RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook and RDM training materials. The exercise was conducted in close collaboration with editorial boards, the ELIXIR Interoperability platform, and the broader RDM community to ensure alignment with current best practices, FAIR principles, and user needs. The deliverable provides insights into the updated body of knowledge and usage, uptake, and impact across ELIXIR RDM resources.

Scope and distribution channels were defined to maximize reach and interoperability, encompassing FAIR Cookbook, RDMkit, the Joint Editorial Board, and related presentations (D2.1) and knowledge models within the Life Sciences Data Stewardship wizard framework. Content added during this IS includes new FAIR Cookbook recipes, RDMkit domain pages, task-oriented guidance, and governance improvements across domain specific topics.

Outcomes indicate substantial engagement, with e.g. the RDMkit attracting thousands of visits and new content drawing significant interest. The consolidation supports policy uptake, training curricula, and capacity-building activities, reinforcing trust and adoption by researchers, funders, and infrastructure providers. Crucially, the work enhances

cross-node collaboration, informs ongoing standardization efforts, and strengthens the European RDM ecosystem by maintaining a living, interoperable body of knowledge.

Document info

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Dissemination level <i>(PU/ RE/CO)</i>	PU

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

EDD	ELIXIR Deposition Database
ETT	ELIXIR Toolkit Theme
FAQ	Frequently Asked Question
RDM	Research Data Management

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Introduction

Task T2.2 aimed to expand and update the best-practice content related to research data management (RDM), particularly focusing on the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook. This task involved collaboration within the editorial boards of the different resources and alignment with the ELIXIR Interoperability platform to ensure that the resources reflect current best practices and community needs.

The outcome is documented in this deliverable D2.2, which serves as the end report on the body of knowledge. This report highlights the updated best practices and provides insights into the utilization of various RDM resources and their new content. Overall, T2.2 effectively enhanced RDM resources within the ELIXIR community, ensuring they remain relevant and valuable for managing research outputs.

Scope of the body of knowledge

The body of knowledge was developed within the scope of synergistic efforts between Interoperability and data platforms and the RDM community.

The platforms for the distribution of the body of knowledge include:

- FAIR Cookbook (<https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/>)
- RDMkit (<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>)
- Joint editorial board (<https://github.com/elixir-europe/faircookbook-rdmkit>)
- Presentations on RDM/Body of knowledge resources (see D2.1 <https://elixir-europe.org/what-we-offer/guidelines/data-management>)
- Life Sciences DSW Knowledge Model (<https://registry.ds-wizard.org/knowledge-models/dsw:lifescience>)

Body of knowledge

Table 1 Body of knowledge

Link to content	Resource	Contributors	Description	# of unique users visiting resource during IS -> 02.12.2025
https://w3id.org/faircookbook/FCB086	FAIR Cookbook recipe	Isabel Kemmer, Maria Mirza	New recipe for the FAIR Cookbook generated by members of the RDM Community	
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/enzymology_and_biocatalysis	RDMkit "your domain" page	Carsten Kettner, Jürgen Pleiss, Johann Rohwer, Hans V. Westerhoff, Ulrike Wittig	New "your domain" page about Enzymology and biocatalysis	85 (matomo)
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/cancer_data	RDMkit "your domain" page	Fátima Al-Shahrour, Erika Schirghuber, Robin Navest, Eva Budinska, Gonzalo Gómez, María González,	New "your domain" page about cancer data	272 (matomo)

		Fotis Psomopoulos, Sarah Morgan, Sophie Huiskes Berends		
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_publication#should-you-include-datasets-accession-numbers-in-pre-prints-or-theses	New paragraph in RDMkit		Should you include datasets accession numbers in pre-prints or theses?	605 (matomo)
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/gr_resources	RDMkit "national resources" page		New "national resources" page for Greece	52 (matomo)
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/creating_dataflow_diagram	RDMkit "your task" page	Vilem Ded	New "your task" page on creating a data-flow diagrams	284 (matomo)
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/human_pat	Update of RDMkit		The "your domain" page was enriched with additional links and a bibliography	306 (matomo)

hogen_genomics	"your domain" page			
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_discoverability	RDMkit "your task page"	Aina Jené Cortada, Laura Portell Silva	New "your task" page on data discoverability	200 (matomo)
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/how_to_contribute	Contribute section update		The Contribute section update with clear ways in how to contribute and improved documentation	913 (matomo)
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/health_data	RDMkit "your domain" page	Marcus Buchwald, Tim Beck, Saskia Lawson-Tovey, Gerhard Mayer, Soumyabrata Ghosh, Philip Quinlan, Venkata Satagopam, Jan Willem Boiten, Patrick Ruch, Hindrik Kerstens, Carlos Luís Parra Calderón, Salvador Capella-Gutierrez,	New "your domain" page about health data	617 (matomo)

		Magda Chegkazi, Arshiya Merchant		
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/machine-learning	RDMkit "your domain" page	Styliani-Christina Fragkouli, Uladzislau Vadadokhau, Adriano Fonzino, Fotis Psomopoulos, Mihaly Varadi, Edward Parkinson, Federico Bianchini, Munazah Andrabi	New "your domain" page about machine learning	398 (matomo)
https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/fairtracks-assembly	RDMkit "tool assembly" page	Federico Bianchini, Sveinung Gundersen	New "tool assembly" page about FAIRtracks	298 (matomo)
https://elixir-europe.org/what-we-offer/guidelines/data-management	ELIXIR website page		RDM guidelines page, including user journeys and FAQs created by the RDM community	758 (google analytics) PDF on zenodo: 549 views, 423 downloads

https://tess.elixir-europe.org/events/training-data-stewards-for-life-sciences	Training Data Stewards for Life Sciences 2025—Session 1	Poiares-Oliveira, Gil; Chaves, Inês	Training course for Data Stewards. Recommended RDMkit as a resource for Data Stewards.	
https://tess.elixir-europe.org/events/ready-for-biodata-management-intensive-course-at-ccmar	Ready for BioData Management: Intensive at CCMAR	Faria, Daniel; Oliveira, Jorge; Poiares-Oliveira, Gil	RDM introduction course for researchers. It closely follows RDMkit.	
https://tess.elixir-europe.org/events/ready-for-biodata-management-intensive-coimbra-2025	Management: Intensive at CCMAR	Faria, Daniel; Oliveira, Jorge; Poiares-Oliveira, Gil	RDM introduction course for researchers. It closely follows RDMkit.	
https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/life-s	Life Science Data	Nazeefa Fatima, Federico Bianchini, David Dolan,	DMP introduction for researchers. Utilizes DSW and RDMkit	

cience-data-managem ent-planning-worksho p	Managem ent: Planning Workshop	Erik Hjerde, Espen Åberg, Korbinian Bösl, Arturo Vera Ponce de Leon		
https://tess.elixir-euro pe.org/materials/life-s cience-rdm-2023-cour se	Life Science RDM 2023 Course - Extended version in 6 modules	Nazeefa Fatima, Federico Bianchini, Korbinian Bösl, Espen Åberg, Illimar Rekand	RDM course for researchers. Utilizes DSW, RDMkit with exercises (including EDD deposition)	
https://doi.org/10.528 1/zenodo.15422659	Interdiscipli nary Open Science competence network in University of Tartu (Estonia) training	Diana Pilvar, Heleri Inno	Launch events for the Data Management and Open Science Competence Network, bringing together nearly 60 participants. Two presentations by ELIXIR Estonia: Heleri Inno's overview of the research data lifecycle (heavily influenced by RDMkit) and Diana Pilvar's examination of RDM-related activities in Europe (including the RDM community).	78 views, 96 downloads (zenodo)

https://tess.elixir-europe.org/events/crash-course-in-data-management-378c69b7-e68d-478b-91fd-1844eb3ccb3	Crash Course in Data Management (eng and est) by ELIXIR EE node	Diana Pilvar	Course structure follows RDMkit logic and uses the content as inspiration with added examples and real life use cases.	1K views, 275 downloads (zenodo)
https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/crash-course-in-data-management-3e39cc22-0f30-4ee5-8b33-8e3ec293d3d2	Crash Course in Data Management (eng and est) by ELIXIR EE node	Heleri Inno	Course structure follows RDMkit logic and uses the content as inspiration with added examples and real life use cases.	297 views, 66 downloads (zenodo)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1733780	From Challenges to Solutions: The	Diana Pilvar	Presented in Latvia for the conference: "Support for the use of data in research: governance, curators, infrastructure". Includes mention of RDMkit and practical insights and personal	64 views, 54 downloads (zenodo)

	Estonian Journey in Research Data Management		narratives from ELIXIR RDM community members, drawing upon experiences originally shared during DATAREX events.	
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Outcomes and expected impact

Outcome (see above)

During the duration of the DATAREX implementation study, e.g. RDMkit was visited by a total of >28k unique users (matomo), while visits to FAIR Cookbook could not be tracked in the same way.

The new content added during this IS to the body of knowledge (see table 1) has experienced considerable interest.

Impact

The "[ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.4 Dissemination of the toolkit across the ERA](#)¹" showed that RDMkit is increasingly referenced in policies, guidelines, and institutional frameworks. We see the same trend for other resources that make up the body of knowledge in DATAREX WP2, confirming their growing relevance for research data management in life sciences. The body of knowledge is not only recommended in multiple policy documents and recommendations, but also used as a resource in one of the first data steward post-graduate degrees curricula².

Keeping this body of knowledge up to date and expanding it is essential for continued trust and adoption by researchers, funders, and infrastructure providers. Regular updates ensure that the content reflects current standards, FAIR principles, and community needs.

This work depends on collaboration across ELIXIR Nodes and communities, supported by editorial boards and the RDM community. These joint efforts not only keep the resources accurate and relevant but also create opportunities for knowledge exchange between RDM professionals and scientific experts. This exchange helps shape practical guidance and strengthens networks across disciplines.

Community input has also improved tools like the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) knowledge models, making them more useful and increasing uptake among different

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7858237>

² Module 3 of the University of Vienna's Data Steward Certificate Course, titled "FAIR Research Data in the Life Cycle", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15423435>

stakeholders. Similarly, the reuse of training materials across platforms and events reduces duplication and ensures consistency. These materials are now being combined into structured learning paths, giving researchers and data stewards clear sequences of learning objectives and modules. This approach speeds up capacity building and supports interoperability between tools and practices.

By maintaining and sharing this body of knowledge, DATAREX WP2 helps researchers apply FAIR and Open Science principles more effectively. It supports sustainable data management, strengthens collaboration, and contributes to a more coherent European Research Area.

Dissemination Plans

Upload to Zenodo within the ELIXIR Zenodo Community.³

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³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/elixir>